

The Significance of Research Methods with Reference to Language Education in Higher Education

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Abstract—This research paper investigates the significance of research in language education in the higher education sector. For this purpose, the researcher conducted a case study with twenty 4th year students studying English at the University of Human Development (UHD), Iraqi Kurdistan Region. They were selected based on purposive sampling. The participants were invited to respond to a questionnaire that was created and piloted by the researcher. They were also requested to take part in a structured interview. The findings show that the nature of research methods for 4th year students across higher education is complex and elusive. The findings also show that most of the students almost have the same problems and they have similar views on their final project as they started at the beginning of the final year of the academic year (2018-2019) at the University of Human Development.

Index terms—Research methods, Reference to language, positivism, post-positivism, interpretivism, epistemology, ontology.

I. INTRODUCTION

This research paper investigates the significance of research methods in language education within higher education and explores the epistemological aspect of social science. It is divided into three main sections. The first focuses on; establishing the justification of the topic as educational research methods in Higher Education (HE) in Iraqi Kurdistan, by arguing that the concepts of the ontology and epistemology and their understanding of theoretical assumptions in research methods. The researcher has justified the choice of methodologies and methods. According to Crotty (1998, p.64) the justification of the choice and use of methodology; plan of action, strategy, design lying behind the use of particular methods and the methods; techniques and analyze data related to the research questions addressed. This allows the researcher to gain an understanding of the research problems and the importance of the study in the field of language education. In section two, the paper critically discusses and assesses the three major paradigms; interpretivism, positivism and post-positivism. In section three, the paper briefly discusses the findings and his own experiences. The paper achieved by focusing on self-reflection and tries to answer the following

main research questions:

1. What are the difficulties that English major 4th year students face in their research papers?
2. What are the most significant strategies of research methods to make students effective in their research writing?

Research Objectives:

The study ultimately aims to:

- Identify the most common difficulties that 4th year students face while writing their research papers.
- Explore the impact of a comprehensive understanding of research methods with reference to language education.

II. THE CONCEPTS OF ONTOLOGY AND EPISTEMOLOGY

This section has two aims: 1) reflections on the idea of 4th year students experience in educational research methods. 2) A discussion on the concepts of ontology and epistemology and their relevance to our understanding of theoretical assumptions. It is vital to place the methodologies within an ontological position and the epistemological as both affect how the methodologies are addressed. The reflections of the underpinning research methods in HE and identify the most difficulties that face students from the 4th year within their research papers that come from the researcher of this paper own experience when he has been teaching in higher education in the UK and in Iraqi Kurdistan Region. Thus, the first reflection which is significant for the 4th year students should be the first question that must be asked in effect what my view of reality is, what is real and what is not? According to Guba (1990, p.34), paradigms can be characterized through their ontology (what is reality), epistemology (how do you know something?) and methodology (how do go about finding out?). Thomas (2009, p.83), points out that ontology is the starting point of all research, after which one's epistemological and methodological positions logically follow.

A. *Ontology*

Ontology has been defined by Thomas (2009, p.85) as: "...a study of what there is or what exists in the social world". While ontology as a general subject is concerned with the being of anything, here we are concerned with the ontology of human beings. According to Gronn, (1999, p.38), specifically, we are concerned with the ontology of research and methods (the nature and function of being a researcher and the actions of effective research). As stated by Thomas (2009, p.98), the starting point for interpretive researchers is to operate within a set of distinctive principles regarding what it means to conduct educational research with people. Thus, the world of the educational researcher is different from the world of the natural science researcher as all educational research needs to be grounded in people's experience. For the interpretivist reality is not out there as a combination of external phenomena waiting to be uncovered as facts, but a construct in which people understand reality in different ways.

B. *Epistemology*

Epistemology is defined by Thomas (2009, p.75) as "...what they think and how they form ideas about the world; how their worlds are constructed". In short, claims about how what is assumed to exist can be known. Derived from the Greek words *episteme* (knowledge) and *logos* (reason), epistemology focuses on the knowledge gathering process and is concerned with developing new models or theories that are better than competing models and theories Blaikie (2000, p.35). Consequently, together, ontological and epistemological assumptions make up a paradigm.

This study has found from literature review there are three contrasting epistemological positions that are those contained within the research paradigms; positivism/post-positivism and interpretivism. It is clear that choosing one of these epistemological positions will lead the researcher to employ a different methodology than he/she would if he/she chose the other. Accordingly, to know this by combining qualitative and quantitative methods that the researcher set up/ interviews/ sending out numbers of questionnaires to get statistical data. Hence, the ways in which knowledge is dependent on the methodology and it has a direct link to the strength of the claim to now knowledge.

C. *The account of research methodology and methods*

Generally speaking, in research within HE and particularly the 4th year students, there are varieties of research methodologies with no single accepted research methodology applicable to all research problems. Hence, each research methodology has its weaknesses and strengths. According to Creswell (2007, p.238), a methodology is "the nature in which their research emerges". Conversely, educational research may be seen as twin-focused. It is a systematic enquiry that is both a distinctive way of thinking about educational phenomena, that is an attitude, and a way of investigating these phenomena, that is action or activity Blaikie (2000, p.117). In terms of a methodology, it seeks to answer the main research questions of how researchers will find out the results. Through this paradigm, the personal conflict of quantitative or qualitative or

both lines of inquiry will be prominent and as with the entire positioning, the decision needs to be prudently considered. Having considered this where researchers likely to position themselves and explained the ontological and epistemological assumptions that drive their decision, it leads them to ask which research methodology.

According to Comte (2000, p.55) stated that in order to build an actionable knowledge base; three research approaches must be considered: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods. Unquestionably, the three approaches are not as discrete as they first appear. Qualitative and quantitative approaches should not be viewed as rigid, distinct categories, opposites, or dichotomies. Instead, they represent different ends of a continuum Newman (2000, p.77). However, mixed methods research resides in the middle of this continuum because it incorporates elements of both qualitative and quantitative approaches.

In this study, the researcher used the mixed methods as an approach to the inquiry involving collecting both qualitative and quantitative data, integrating the two forms of data, and using distinct designs that may involve philosophical assumptions and theoretical frameworks.

The next stage is to reflect the ontological and epistemological assumptions that underpin both qualitative and quantitative approaches. There is also evidence to suggest that many contemporary instances of mixture methods take place without explicitly or formally acknowledging that the practical and philosophical premises Bryman (2006, p.88). In terms of an ontological assumption, when using a mixed method approach researchers believe that there is a reality that can be understood. The researcher of this study believes this approach is useful for gaining an understanding of the research problem and the corroboration of findings. Oppositely, the research cannot simply be explained by cause and effect; it is interpreted in a variety of ways. The justification of chosen mixed methods is a logic of inquiry that includes the use of induction (the discovery of patterns) deduction (i.e. the testing of theories and hypotheses) and abduction (uncovering and relying on the best of a set of explanations for understanding one's results). This is because of its logical and intuitive appeal, this approach provides a bridge between the qualitative and quantitative paradigms (Johnson et al 1997, p.93). On the other hand, there are many advantages to using this approach in higher education. Thus, it can help the researcher to answer research questions that cannot be answered by qualitative or quantitative approaches alone Creswell (2007, p.123). Conversely, it is argued that the mixed methods approach can increase the generalizability of the results. It allows researchers to be more flexible, integrative and holistic in their investigative techniques Bryaman (2006, p.56). Accordingly, this study is a benefit for a researcher to use the epistemological assumptions to help further in order to help the decision. If a researcher will use a quantitative approach, so he/she would be independent of the research and so any relationships can be accounted for an explained, whereas with a qualitative approach there is very much being researched, essentially the findings are a result of the interactions. Hence, having decided that an exclusive mixed method is most sustainable, the strengths and weaknesses of using either qualitative or quantitative approach need to be analyzed in Higher education within Iraqi Kurdistan Region.

